

THE INFLUENCE OF A POLYMER MATRIX AND POLYMER COATINGS ON THE STRENGTH OF
SILICON CARBIDE REINFORCING FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

A study has been made of the strength and fracture behaviour of a 100 μm diameter silicon carbide fibre (14 μm tungsten core), when tested as a single filament and when coated with various thicknesses of an epoxy resin. The single fibre was found to have a bi-modal fracture behaviour based around surface and core initiated failures. When coated with resin, however, surface initiated failure was inhibited, to such an extent that in fibres coated with 1-2 mm of resin, only core initiated failures were observed. The fibre was found to have a residual surface tensile stress in its as-manufactured state; the change in fracture behaviour may be due to thermal contraction of the resin, during curing, reducing this stress.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of statistical work on composite materials has centred on two fields; 1) the strength of single filaments of high modulus fibres such as carbon, glass etc., and 2) the strength of laminated coupons of these fibres impregnated with a resin phase. Relatively little experimental work has been carried out on accurately relating the former to the latter. This is largely due to the geometric complexity of most composite materials, where even in unidirectional coupons, fibres are packed together at random making exact analysis of the load distribution within a large sample almost impossible.

The strength of high modulus ceramic fibres is governed by flaws on the surface and within the bulk of the filament. The more severe a flaw the lower the strength of that section of material. If these flaws are assumed

to be distributed randomly along the fibre, then a long length is more likely to contain a serious defect than a short length. A long fibre will thus appear statistically weaker than a short one.

To describe this behaviour a statistical function which allows for this "strength/length" effect must be used. The two-parameter Weibull distribution meets these requirements:

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{x}{x_0} \right)^W \right] \quad (1)$$

where x = failure stress or strain, L_0 is the length at which x_0 the Weibull scale parameter and W the shape parameter were measured and L is the length of fibre under investigation. For a filament which fails due to a distribution of a single flaw type, a plot of $\text{LnLn}(1/(1-P_f))$ vs $\text{Ln}(x)$ should give a straight line with gradient W and intercept x_0 at $\text{LnLn}(1/(1-P_f))=0$, (see Figure 3b). Data from different gauge lengths would appear as a series of parallel lines displaced from each other since the shorter fibres will have higher x_0 values.

When a fibre is embedded in a resin matrix its failure behaviour is modified. A continuous filament assumed to be well bonded to the matrix will extend uniformly and as the applied load is increased it will fracture at the most severe defect. This will cause a redistribution of stress in the region of the break. Stress will be diffused back into the fibre over a length which is a function of the matrix shear modulus and the interfacial bonding. This length is usually termed the "ineffective length" after the model of

Rosen [1], figure 1a. The parts of the fibre beyond this "ineffective length" will still be loaded to the stress at which the fracture occurred. Further loading may cause fracture at less severe defects within these parts of the fibre, giving a stress distribution in the fibre similar to figure 1b.

Figure 1 Tensile stress distribution in an embedded fibre which has failed
(a) once at strain ϵ_1 and,
(b) again at strain ϵ_2 ($\epsilon_2 > \epsilon_1$)

In this work tensile testing of embedded single fibres and of unsupported filaments suggested that the strength distribution function for

the fibre was different in the two states. This has been investigated in more detail by testing fibres coated with resin layers from 5 μm to 2mm thick and examining the distribution of fibre failure strains in each.

MATERIALS

In order to measure the properties of long lengths of single fibres it is convenient to use a large diameter filament which can be easily handled. For this work a 100 μm diameter chemical vapour deposition (CVD) produced silicon carbide (SiC) fibre (14 μm tungsten core) was used in preference to the smaller carbon and glass fibres. This filament is produced by Sigma GmbH and may be tested in lengths of up to 1m, although it is very sensitive to surface damage [2] and great care must be exercised when handling it.

A flexibilised epoxy resin matrix has been used for coating fibres. This system was chosen so that in coupons several mm thick containing a single filament, fibre fractures could be contained with only localised damage to the matrix. Non-flexibilised epoxy resins were found to be too brittle and cracks propagated in an uncontrolled and catastrophic manner from fibre breaks. In addition the high transparency and good photo-elastic behaviour of this resin simplify observation of fibre failures and associated events.

FABRICATION AND TESTING METHODS

Single fibre tensile test specimens were produced using a conventional window-card technique. Fibres were glued to cards with cut-outs of 10, 50 100 and 500 mm using an epoxy adhesive. Samples were loaded in a screw driven tensile testing machine fitted with pneumatic grips. The grips were instrumented with a matched pair of LVD transducers so that grip separation could be monitored without having to allow for the stiffness of the loading system.

The diameter of each fibre was measured using a micrometer, this being found to give comparable results to laser diffraction and optical microscope techniques. In each test failure load and extension were measured and the fibre failure stress and elastic modulus calculated.

Fibres with thin (5-50 μm) coatings of epoxy resin were produced by forming a continuous loop of $\approx 5\text{m}$ of fibre and then passing this repeatedly

through a resin bath and a vertical tube furnace. Each pass through this system applied $\approx 5\mu\text{m}$ of partially cured resin to the fibre. The complete coating was fully cured by a further heating cycle. Samples were then cut out of the loop, mounted and testing in the same way as the uncoated single filament.

Coupons 4mm thick with a single fibre embedded so that it was aligned down the centre were produced by casting sheets of epoxy resin between glass plates. Fibres were glued to an aluminium frame which was sealed between the plates, the resulting mould filled with resin and hot cured. Tensile test pieces were then cut from the finished plate so that the fibre was positioned along the centre of the coupon.

When tested these samples were observed in polarised light. Fibre failures could easily be observed owing to the local photo-elastic pattern induced in the resin. Failure strain was monitored using a resistance strain gauge on the coupon surface and an approximate correction made for the axial thermal constraint imposed on the fibre by the resin shrinkage during cure.

RESULTS

Single Fibre Tests

Load/extension curves for single filaments were linear to failure at all gauge lengths. The elastic moduli taken from these curves showed no systematic variation with gauge length. The mean value from all 195 tests was 338 GPa, (sd: 13.5 GPa). The mean value of the fibre diameter was $103\mu\text{m}$ (sd: $1.3\mu\text{m}$).

The fibre failure strains from the tests at all four gauge lengths are plotted against failure probability in figure 2. This figure also shows the results of a series of tests at one gauge length on the $14\mu\text{m}$ tungsten filament used the fibre core. The data has been plotted on strain axes rather than stress to allow direct comparison between the different types of test. The plot shows the "length effect" expected in this type of material in that the shorter gauge lengths exhibit higher mean strengths. There is, however, considerable overlap between the distributions and this coupled with their uneven shape suggests that the data is the result of a complex mixture of flaw types.

Figures 3a and 3b show the 100mm and 10mm data plotted on both strain

vs probability axes and $\ln(\text{strain})$ vs $\ln\ln(1/(1-P_f))$ or "Weibull probability" axes. The straight lines on this second plot are linear least squares fits to the data and the Weibull parameter estimates from these lines were used to generate the cumulative distribution function lines in figure 3a. Examination of these two figures shows some deviation from the ideal Weibull behaviour, particularly in the 10mm data, and indicates at least two distinct regions to the distribution function. Similar patterns may be observed in the other data sets in figure 2. The estimated Weibull parameters for all the single fibre distributions are shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficients (r) from the $\ln/\ln\ln$ plots give a measure of the accuracy of the model. By weak link scaling the data using equation 1 the parameter estimates for the 100mm distribution give $\epsilon_0 = 1.08\%$ for a 10mm distribution. Similarly the 10mm parameter estimates give $\epsilon_0 = 0.37\%$ for a 100mm distribution. The discrepancy between these and the measured values of 0.84% and 0.60% (Table 1 and figure 3b) also indicate the inadequacy of the two-parameter Weibull model.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) examination of fibre fracture surfaces showed two distinct failure initiation points. Failure at low ($<0.7\%$) strain were found to be caused by defects on the fibre surface (figure 4). At higher strains ($>1\%$) fracture appeared to initiate at the tungsten core of the material (figure 5).

Figure 4 SEM image of surface defect initiated fibre fracture

Figure 5 SEM image of core initiated fibre fracture surface

Figure 3a Uncoated fibre data from 100 mm and 10 mm tests with fitted Weibull cumulative distribution functions

Figure 3b Data from 3a plotted on 'Weibull probability' or Ln/LnLn axes with straight lines fitted by linear regression

These failures were observed most frequently at the upper end of the data for the 10mm gauge length distribution. The 10mm fibres were, of course, stronger than the others due to their shorter length. It should also be noted that in contrast to the longer gauge lengths the upper part of the 10mm distribution appears to show a distinct cut-off at $\approx 1.1\%$ strain.

Coated and Embedded Fibres

Failure strain data for 50mm gauge fibres with 5, 30 and 40 μm coatings of resin are shown in figure 6. These distributions all show a similar discrete cut-off at the upper end at 1-1.1% strain and in this respect resemble the 10mm uncoated fibres. Figure 7 shows data from 100mm fibres with 5 μm and 2mm coatings of resin. The dotted line on this figure represents the position of the embedded data distribution if the maximum estimate for thermal constraint is applied. The 5 μm coated fibre distribution again shows a discrete cut-off although at a lower level than the 5 μm coated 50mm gauge fibres ($\approx 0.8\%$). The embedded material, however, has a very narrow strength distribution with variability similar to that of the tungsten core alone. The Weibull parameter estimates for these distributions are shown in Table 1 and the values of the Ln/LnLn correlation coefficients again show the inaccuracy of the model.

SEM examination of fracture surfaces from the 5, 30 and 40 μm coated fibres suggests that the majority of failures at higher strains originate at the core of the filament. The fracture surfaces of all the embedded fibres examined showed core initiated failures.

DISCUSSION

The data for the uncoated fibres show a strength/length effect but conform only superficially to a simple two-parameter Weibull model, (figures 2 and 3). The deviation from ideal Weibull behaviour is more significant at the shorter gauge lengths and SEM examination of fibre fracture surfaces suggests that this is probably due to a bi-modal fracture mechanism based on core and surface initiated failures. Although the cumulative distribution functions appear visually similar to a bi-modal Weibull distribution after the model of Fukunaga [3], it is only possible to fit this type of complex function if the failure initiation site for each fracture is known. It was not practicable to make this observation in every case.

Comparison of the data for coated 50mm gauge and uncoated 10mm gauge fibres (figure 8) shows that the upper ends of these distributions terminate at a strain level of approximately 1.1%. Also shown on this figure is the estimated line for the 100mm embedded data distribution after thermal constraint correction. This line is also centred at $\approx 1.1\%$ strain. The coefficients of variation calculated from the gradients of the upper sections of these distributions on a Weibull plot, are very similar to the tungsten core distribution ($\approx 8-10\%$) and this coupled with the SEM examination of fracture surfaces suggests that coating the fibre inhibits surface initiated low-strain failures.

A fibre polished in half along its core axis was found to bend due to the internal stress in the material. This curvature shows that the surface of the fibre had a residual tensile stress and the core was in compression. Coating the fibre with an epoxy resin would impose a constraint due to shrinkage of the resin on curing, which would act to reduce this surface stress. Increasing the coating thickness will increase the degree of constraint. This agrees well with the measured data, where the more thickly coated fibres exhibit an increasing proportion of core initiated failures. In the embedded filament no surface initiated failures have been observed at all.

In tests on the tungsten core alone considerable plastic deformation and necking of the filament was observed before final fracture. This behaviour in the core of a brittle filament would cause fracture of the complete fibre, however figures 2, 8 and Table 1 show that the sections of the distributions attributed to core initiated fractures have characteristic failure strains $\approx 0.2\%$ greater than the characteristic core yield strain. Although the SiC imposes a compressive stress on the core, this alone is not enough to explain the size of this discrepancy. The SEM examination of core initiated failures shows that the core fractures in a brittle manner (figure 5), and it is possible that this is due to the high temperature (1200°C) CVD process causing embrittlement of the metal filament. Since the tungsten appears well bonded to the SiC, it is also probable that the latter imposes a radial constraint on the core. This will cause the core to be loaded in a state analogous to plane strain and the tungsten is likely to fail in a brittle manner at a strain above its normal yield strain. Further examination of these points will form a part of future work in this project.

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TABLE 1

gauge mm	coating thickness	n	W	ϵ_0 %	Cv %	r
Single fibres						
500	-	50	3.17	0.55	33.8	0.979
100	-	30	3.91	0.60	27.8	0.987
50	-	90	3.72	0.71	29.1	0.993
10	-	25	2.77	0.84	38.4	0.938
Coated fibres						
100	5 μ m	18	3.85	0.67	28.2	0.963
50	5 μ m	39	4.89	0.92	22.5	0.987
50	30 μ m	46	8.62	0.97	13.2	0.990
50	40 μ m	30	6.39	1.05	17.5	0.913
Embedded fibre						
100	2mm	8	25.5	1.22	4.76	0.972
Tungsten core						
50	-	39	13.9	0.79*	8.42	0.946

* ϵ_0 for core is measured yield strain not failure strain.

n - number of observations.

r - correlation coefficient on Weibull Ln/LnLn plot.

Figure 2 Failure strains of uncoated SiC filaments tested at four different gauge lengths. The figure also shows data for the yield strain of the W-core tested at 50mm gauge length

Figure 6 Failure strain data for 50mm gauge fibres with 0, 5, 30 and 40 μm resin coatings

Figure 7 Failure strain data for 100mm gauge uncoated, coated and embedded fibres. The dotted line represents the estimated maximum thermal constraint correction for the embedded material

Figure 8 Failure strain data for 10 mm single fibres, 50 mm coated fibres and 100 mm embedded material showing discrete cut-off at $\approx 1.1\%$